

Isolation, pathogenicity, and characterization of *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* (Sacc. & Magnus) Briosi & Cavara

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Abstract— The present investigation was undertaken to study anthracnose disease of black gram (*Vigna mungo* L. Hepper) caused by *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* (Sacc. and Magnus) Briosi and Cavara which is quite destructive in all the black gram growing areas. Generally, black gram is widely cultivated in India in the *kharif* and summer season. In normal conditions, it is grown as a rain-fed crop. Black gram-infected plants showing typical symptoms of anthracnose were collected from a University farm and isolated on a PDA medium. Based on cultural and morphological characters, it was identified as *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* and further confirmed with molecular identification based on 18s rDNA ITS sequencing.

Keywords— Black gram, Anthracnose, *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum*, *kharif*, Symptoms, Characterization

I. INTRODUCTION

Black gram (*Vigna mungo* (L.) Hepper) is one of the most important pulse crops in India. Pulses greatly enhance the security and safety of food. With an area of about 20 percent, it makes up 7–10% of all food grain production. Grown as a *kharif* crop in tropical and subtropical regions, black gram [*Vigna mungo* (L.) Hepper], sometimes called urd bean, mash, or black maple, is an annual, semi-erect to spreading herb of the Fabaceae family [11]. Around 93.18 (Mha) of total world acreage is planted to pulses, yielding 89.82 (MT) at a yield level of 964 kg/ha. With more than 28 million hectares dedicated to pulse cultivation, India is the world's largest producer of these crops. With 31% of the total area and 28% of the output, it leads in both categories. Our productivity, which was 885 kg/ha in 2020–21, has also significantly increased over the previous five years [15]. Among different restricting factors, diseases are major constrain in economic production as they cause heavy losses. Among various diseases infecting black gram, the anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* is now a day become a major limiting factor in black gram cultivation, especially in the *kharif* season. One significant aspect of increasing output is the early and prompt detection and diagnosis of those diseases [6]. The causal organism of pulse anthracnose, *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* Sacc. and Magnus) Lams. Scrib. is a serious soil-born and seed-borne pathogen of pulse crops worldwide. It has been reported to occur on *kharif* pulses in several countries, including Nigeria, India, Thailand, Philippines, Upper Volta, Zambia, Palmira, and Columbia [1]. In cool, humid environments, *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* was causing significant yield losses of around 80–100% [25]. The present research was aimed to: (i) assess anthracnose symptoms in the surveyed black gram growing area of Junagadh; (ii) use morphological, cultural, and molecular techniques to characterize the *Colletotrichum* spp. causing anthracnose on the Black gram in Junagadh, and (iii) determining the pathogenicity of the species on the Black gram.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Collection of diseased specimens

Infected pods and leaves of black gram were collected from the farmer's fields and university fields. These specimens were brought to the laboratory, Department of Plant Pathology, Junagadh Agricultural University, Junagadh in butter paper bags and used for isolation of the pathogen.

B. Microscopic observation

Diseased spots were examined under the microscope after teasing with a sharp blade in a drop of clear water on a clean slide covered with a cover slip and observed under a binocular research microscope (40X) to confirm the presence of fungal spores and fruiting bodies.

C. Isolation

Black gram pods and leaves infected with anthracnose disease which showed typical symptoms were first microscopically examined to confirm the presence of the fungus. Isolation of the fungi was made by tissue isolation technique. Small pieces of tissues from infected leaves and pods (3 mm) along with some healthy tissues were cut using a sterilized scalpel and the cut tissues were surface sterilized with 1 percent sodium hypochlorite solution for about 30 to 45 seconds. They were then washed three times with sterilized distilled water to remove the excess of sodium hypochlorite [19]. Finally, they were transferred under aseptic conditions onto Petri plates containing solidified potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium and incubated at 27 ± 2 °C [18]. The resulting fungal cultures were purified by the hyphal tip method. Purified cultures of test pathogens were maintained on PDA slants by storing them under refrigeration at 4 °C. To maintain the cultures for further studies, periodical transfers were made once a month. The fungi were isolated, purified, and subcultured in aseptic conditions under a laminar flow.

D. Identification of the fungus

Pathogens primarily identified by morphological characters such as mycelial and cultural characters, mode of conidial production, conidiophores, and length and breadth of conidia, were studied by using a microscope [8].

E. Proving the pathogenicity

Pathogenicity tests were carried out to establish that the fungi isolated from infected plant tissues are capable of producing typical symptoms of anthracnose and under artificial inoculation conditions on black gram leaves and pods and also to prove Koch's postulates of the pathogen.

The cultures multiplied on PDA were scraped using a sterilized surgical scalpel and transferred into 10 ml sterilized distilled water under aseptic conditions. The tubes were shaken for 15 minutes, to get a uniform, homogenized spore suspension and also to break the mycelial clumps if any.

For the study, the plants were grown in earthen pots, filled with soil. The soil was autoclaved at 15 lbs psi for 30 minutes. Simultaneously, the pots were sterilized with a 4 percent formalin solution, and autoclaved soil was filled in these pots. Healthy seeds of black gram variety GU-1 were surface sterilized with 0.1% HgCl₂ and sown @ 10 seeds per pot and repeated five times. The pots were watered regularly. Leaves stem and branches of six-week-old plants randomly selected were injured gently by brush and the ten-day-old culture suspensions of the pathogen (5×10^5 cfu/ml) were sprayed through a hand Atomizer in the morning [14]. Simultaneously, an inoculated check was maintained by spraying sterilized distilled water only. Plants were observed daily to record the incubation period for the disease incidence. The pathogen was re-isolated from the infected seedlings which showed typical symptoms of disease development and the culture so obtained was compared with original cultures.

F. Cultural, morphological, and molecular characterization of *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum*

1) Cultural studies

The isolated pathogen was purified through the hyphal tip technique on PDA slants and stored in the refrigerator (40C) for further studies. This pathogen was separately grown on PDA in Petri plates for seven days for further study. A cultural study for pathogens was conducted on PDA (200 g potato, 20 g dextrose, 20 g agar, and 1000 ml distilled water) in Petri plates (90 mm). The plates were inoculated centrally with 5 mm culture discs taken from the periphery of the seven-day-old culture and incubated at 27 ± 2 °C. Cultural characteristics such as colony diameter, mycelium, colony color, and pigmentation were recorded [8].

2) Morphological studies

A small amount of culture of test pathogen obtained from a ten-day-old culture was placed on the slide and teased thoroughly with lacto phenol to obtain uniform spread. A cover slip was placed over it. Length and breadth of 20 conidia were measured under Olympus Digital Microscope and the average sizes were calculated [5].

Morphological studies of test pathogen (*Colletotrichum* sp.) were conducted on PDA media. A spore's characteristics such as colour, size, and shape were recorded primarily with the help of a simple compound microscope.

3) Molecular identification

The test pathogen (*C. lindemuthianum*) was identified based on molecular method. For genome sequencing, fungal genomic DNA was extracted from the pure culture of the test pathogen grown in 250 ml of PDB at 27 °C for 7 days by using the method described by [21]. The mycelia were harvested from broth and lyophilized and stored at -20 °C for further processing. The

genomic DNA for PCR was extracted by using a QIAamp DNA mini kit fungi DNA isolation kit. The ITS region of fungi, including ITS1 (5'TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG3') and ITS4 (5'TCCTCCGCTTTATTGATATG3') were amplified. The amplification was performed in 30 µl reaction volume with 0.1 mM of each dNTP and 100 pmol of both forward and reverse primer. ABI Veriti PCR was programmed for initial de-naturation at 94 °C for 4 min, and 35 cycles at 94 °C for 1 min, 55 °C for 1 min, and 72 °C for 1 min. The amplification was completed with a final extension at 72 °C for 5 min. Further, it was sequenced by ABI 3730 capillary sequencing.

After sequencing identification of fungal sequence was analysed using BLAST (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>).

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

G. Symptomology

Anthraxnose disease of black gram is endemic in high-rainfall areas. Older leaves of the plants are more susceptible to disease. The disease symptoms are mostly confined to the leaf blade, but under severe conditions, the symptoms develop on the stem, petiole, and pods.

1) On leaves:

The disease first appeared in the field as two to three small pinhead dots like circular red-colored spots on the leaves. As the development of the disease progresses, the spots enlarge, become brown, and finally angular and light brown with a dark red or brownish margin and a gray center. Over time, the spots coalesced together forming 5-6 mm necrotic areas. After a spell of rain, the entire leaf blade was covered with disease spots followed by the formation of “shot holes” and shedding down papery necrotic areas.

Plants ultimately suffered premature defoliation. Younger leaves were relatively resistant to infection but became susceptible to disease gradually with their increasing age. The disease infection in the leaves is generally conceded with the time when plants have begun flowering but infection may set in even before infection in a few cases. Under high moisture stress, the disease symptoms were also observed on the stem, petiole, and pods. The disease spots produced on the petiole were small reddish brown 1-4 mm in diameter. On the stem, the disease lesions initially appeared as water-soaked irregular light-colored spots, which gradually enlarged up to 10-14 mm in diameter and became brown.

2) On pods

On pods, characteristic small rust-colored circular spots were produced. Heavily infected pods sometimes showed twisting. Numerous brown to blackish areas containing reproductive structures were formed on the pods. Depending on how early black gram plants were infected, the plants showed variability in reduction in height, leaf number, and biomass. Diseased plants showed relatively few numbers of flowers and pods in comparison to healthy plants of black gram (Fig.1).

Defoliation of the infected leaves, followed by weakening of the pods, results in “die back” caused by necrosis of tender twigs from the tip to backward. The entire branch, the entire tip, or the whole plant may wither away. These symptoms were more or less similar to the symptoms described by Tripathi and Beniwal, (1977) and Sumit Kumar (2014) while working with anthracnose of black gram and similar observations recorded by Laxman, (2000), Kulkarni, (2009) and Sharma et al. (2012) while working with anthracnose of green gram.

Fig. 1 Symptoms of anthracnose disease on leaves, stem and pods

H. Isolation of the pathogen

The diseased samples were collected in the *Kharif* season from severely infected plants of JAU farm and different villages of Junagadh districts to explore the possibility of variable populations of the black gram pathogen *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum*. The farmers of this area mostly grow GU-1 variety of black gram. Some farmers raise crops from seeds, saved from the harvest of the previous season's crop. The pathogen isolated from different plant samples was used in this present study.

The isolation was carried out as per the technique mentioned in the "Materials and Methods". Reddish brown to purple growth of the fungal mycelia appeared on the media after 2-3 days of incubation at 27 °C which turned dark after seven days. Microscopic observation of fungal growth had shown typical *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* conidia and acervuli in abundance amount.

While working on urdbean, Mishra *et al.* (1992) and Aggrawal *et al.* (2019) isolated *C. lindemuthianum* from infected plants. The same pathogen was also isolated from common beans [3,4,20 and 16], green gram [9 and 7] and cowpea [23] by different researchers.

The culture was purified by a single spore isolation technique as mentioned in the previous chapter and maintained for further study.

I. Primary identification of isolated pathogens

Primary identification of the isolated fungus was done based on morphological characters. The fungus in the present study produced septate mycelium. Later, it produced conidia and conidiophores arising singly or closely packed together in rows. Conidiophores were single-celled, hyaline, and aseptate with one or several conidial scars. The conidia were oblong or cylindrical or slightly dumbbell, hyaline, and aseptate with rounded ends with one to two oil globules in the conidium (Fig.2).

J. Proving pathogenicity

The fungus was isolated from an infected black gram plant and pure culture was obtained by single spore isolation method as described in the methodology part and such culture was used for the pathogenicity test of Koch's postulates.

This was conducted to prove the pathogenicity of the isolate of *C. lindemuthianum* obtained from diseased black gram plants. Symptoms on infected leaves of black gram, lesions were reddish brown to dark brown in the beginning, later these spots became enlarged in size. Spots were circular to irregular in shape with grey centers. The spotted portion became papery with defoliation of leaves producing "shot-holes". The identical culture of *C. lindemuthianum* was again recovered on re-isolation from the diseased leaves.

Thus, the test pathogen was confirmed as *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum*, and the pathogenicity of *C. lindemuthianum* was proved. Observations of the pathogenicity test of the present study matched with earlier reports of Aggarwal *et al.* (2019) and Sardhara, (2015) while working with anthracnose of black gram. Also Kulkarni, (2009) proved the pathogenicity of *C. lindemuthianum* on green gram.

K. Cultural, morphological, and molecular characterization of *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum*

1) Cultural characterization

To study the cultural characteristics, the isolate of *C. lindemuthianum* was grown on PDA in Petri plate and inoculated with a 5 mm culture disc taken from the periphery of the seven-day-old culture. Observations on cultural characters viz., colony color, growth pattern, pigmentation, and sporulation were recorded a week after injection (Fig.2)

The color of the colony was observed from the reverse side of the Petri plate. The observations on colony pigmentation were taken eight days after incubation. The observation showed that the culture was initially whitish, later on, it became purple to dark brown. It was good growth and smooth margin to irregular margin on, potato dextrose agar (PDA).

2) Spore morphology

Conidial morphological characters of *C. lindemuthianum* were recorded from the seven to ten-day-old cultures. Spore size was measured with the help of a Digital Olympus microscope. For the measurement of spore, a total of 20 observations were taken for the pathogens and the average of observations was calculated.

The conidia of *C. lindemuthianum* were hyaline, single-celled, smooth-walled, oblong, and rod-shaped. The length of conidia ranged between 10.2- 18.52 µm and the breadth of 3.1-6.5 µm under the 40X microscopic observation. The average length of 20 conidia was 14.46 µm whereas the average breadth of 20 conidia was 5.13 µm observed (Fig.2).

The fungus was identified as *C. lindemuthianum* as all the cultural and morphological characters matched up well with the characters of *C. lindemuthianum* reported by Gautam *et al.* (2012) on black gram and Quimio (1975) on green gram crop.

Fig. 1 Cultural and morphological characterization of *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* fungus

3) Molecular identification

Genome sequencing of the ITS region was done as mentioned in the Methodology part. For identification, the sequence was performed BLAST on NCBI (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>), and similarity with other species was computed.

The BLAST analysis of the ITS sequence data supported the morphological identification. Further, the sequence was submitted to gene bank NCBI and it was accepted by NCBI with accession number MW856786. Hence, the results of this study revealed that the test fungus isolated from the infected leaves and pods of black gram from Junagadh Agricultural University was *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* (Sacc. & Magn.) Briosi & Cavara.

Table 1: Sequence data of *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* isolated from black gram

Pathogen	Sequence	NCBI Accession number
<i>Colletotrichum lindemuthianum</i>	ATGATCCCTCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGGAGGGATCATTACCGAGTTTACAACCTCCCAAACC CCTGTGAACATAACCACTTGTTCCTCGGCGGATCAGCCCGCTCCCGGTTAAAACGGGACGG CCCGCCAGAGGACCCCTAAACTCTGTTTCTATATGTAACCTCTGAGTAAAACCATAAATA AATCAAAAACCTTTCAACAACGGATCTCTTGGTTCTGGCATCGATGAAGAACGCAGCAAAT GCGATAAGTAATGTGAATTGCAGAATTCAGTGAATCATCGAATCTTTGAACGCACATTGC GCCCCGACAGTATTCTGGCGGGCATGCCTGTTCGAGCGTCATTTCAACCCTCAAGCCCTCGG TTTTGGTGTGGGGATCGGCGAGCCCTTTGCGGCAAGCCGGCCCCGAAATCTAGTGGCGG TCTCGCTGCAGCTTCCATTGCGTAGTAGTAAAACCCTCGCAACTGGTACGCGGGCGCGGCC AAGCCGTTAAACCCCAACTTCTGAATG TTGACCTCGG ATCAGGTTCGGAAGCCCCC GGG	MW856786

IV. CONCLUSION

The infected plant exhibits mostly foliar disease symptoms which become severe under a cool and humid atmosphere. Young as well as old plants are equally vulnerable. Anthracnose of black gram has been constantly observed in severe form for the past few years in different parts of Gujarat. In the case of the disease spectrum of this crop, it has been observed that anthracnose is most important being endemic in high rainfall areas. The disease causes “shot holes” in leaves resulting in large-scale premature defoliation. It is one of the major diseases responsible for lowering the yield of the crop. The anthracnose appeared at different growth stages of the crop.

The pathogen associated with anthracnose of black gram was isolated from the infected plant parts on the PDA medium. Samples were collected from the University farms and local farms around Junagadh city and identified as *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* based on standard mycological keys and confirmed with molecular identification. The pathogenicity of the isolate was also proved. The symptom of anthracnose of black gram was characterized by distinct lesions on leaves and petioles. The symptoms were observed in all aerial parts of the plants from the seedling stage of crop growth. The fungus produces dark brown to black sunken lesions on the hypocotyl area and causes death of seedlings. Small angular brown lesions appear on leaves, mostly adjacent to veins, which later become the grayish-white center with dark brown or reddish margin.

Cultures of *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* showed cottony white to purple colored sparse mycelial growth with smooth margins and later on, became dark brown with good sporulation on PDA media. The spores of *C. lindemuthianum* were hyaline, single-celled, oblong, and rod-shaped with 10.2- 18.52 μm length and 3.1-6.5 μm breadth. Later on, the isolate was identified with the help of molecular ITS region sequencing as *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* (Sacc. & Magn.) with accession number MW856786.

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